

Strategies of Imperial Control and Their Lasting Footprints

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Abstract	The article traces in detail the deployment and exercise of complex array of strategies by the Colonial Government - for creation of network of surveillance by which Imperial control expanded, sustained and consolidate their authority in India. The paper highlights the unearthing of pre-colonial past initiated through generations of European scholarly endeavour which was transformed in official discourse of Manuals, Gazettes to support Colonial realpolitik. After 1857, British raj became more security conscious, thereby increasingly employed statistical and ethnographic information to attempt to better control the large swathes of people and territory. In this process the project objectified social, cultural, linguistic differences among the people of India, contributed decisively to the formation of highly influential stereotypes and modes of classification for the sake of ruling. The article also examines how Colonial constructs became embedded in and continue to inform contemporary political, social, legal and economic structures.
Keywords	Colonial Realpolitik, Statistical and Ethnographic Information, Cultural, Linguistic differences, Stereotypes.
Introduction	<p>Colonial conquest was not just the result of power of superior military organizations, political acumen or economic wealth. It was made possible, sustained and strengthened much by cultural technologies. In certain important ways, knowledge was what Colonialism was all about. [1]</p> <p>Long before Michel Foucault theoretical proposals of knowledge and information as property linked to power opened up provocative discussion by Edward Said on the relation between power and knowledge in Colonial discourse and Oriental scholarship. An Anthropological perspective was applied by Cohn to the Colonial forms of knowledge regarding India, ranging from pre-colonial durbars in Delhi to enumerative technologies and power deployed by the Census.[2]</p> <p>However, Alternatively C.A. Baley's study dealt from the premise that the information order of different societies cannot be viewed simply as a discursive property of the power of the elite and the State. It is rather relatively an autonomous domain constituted not only by the State surveillance and elite ideological representations but also by affective communities of religion, beliefs, kinship, pilgrimage, literary or linguistic sensibilities which combined in the system of surveillance of the emerging State. [3]</p>
Objective of study	The paper highlights the unearthing of pre-colonial past initiated through generations of European scholarly endeavour which was transformed in official discourse of Manuals, Gazettes to support Colonial realpolitik.
Review of Literature	<p><i>Modern Times: India 1880s-1950s</i> by Sumit Sarkar, 2014 has given detailed analysis in the chapter titled <i>knowledge and Governance</i> on the mechanisms of Imperial control. His critical insights on multiple and highly diverse sections on law, census, education, science gives inputs for this article.</p> <p>Another important work titled <i>Colonialism and its form of Knowledge, The British in India</i>, by Bernard. S. Cohn, 1996, deals exclusively with how colonial Government sustained and consolidated their position through diverse mechanisms. The author has identified and explored diverse cultural mechanisms which orchestrated the expansion, sustenance and consolidation of the empire.</p> <p>Additionally; C. A. Bayly's work <i>Empire and Information; Intelligence Gathering and Social Communication in India 1780-1870</i>, 1996 is one of the pioneering works on information order of British India. This book deals with the Colonial power based on surveillance network combined with native contributions.</p>

Further, Vinay Lal work *The History of History: Politics and Scholarships in Modern India*, 2003 also give insights on the subject.

Orientalism and the Postcolonial Predicament: Perspective on South Asias ed., by Carol A. Breckenridge and Peeter Van Der Veer; 1993 an edited volume that explores the strength critique and relevance of Colonial I understanding of south Asia and how Colonial constructs continue to affect social cultural political sphere of the contemporary India.

Main Text

One of the relevant sites of colonial knowledge had indigenous influence. After taking over the conquered territories, British not only built their intelligence network but tapped internal espionage and political reporting system which had long been deployed by precolonial Mughal and local kingdoms of the Indian subcontinent. British learned the art of listening on the internal communication through slow and piecemeal process.[4]

Important theme in Indian political thought was surveillance. The major ancient Sanskrit text *kamandaki nitisara* composed between 400-600 AD on statecraft and political ethics presents significance of systematic surveillance as political prudence. It advocated for multiple channels of information otherwise king risks being blindsided. The text was copied many times over the following millennium in India, Burma and Java explicitly linking political intelligence and state craft with spying.[5]

After 1200 AD a more regular system of official political reporting was gradually introduced and a comprehensive grid of regular posts were established under recognised officials. Survey of Indian religion society culture and science and technology was initiated by collating personal observation and interviews with the high priest of different communities. The Arab travellers Alberuni and Ibn Batuta had pioneered this tradition.[6]

Abul Fazel during Mughal emperor Akbar's reign compiled similar information in his 16th century *Ain- I – Akbari*, the regulations of Akber. In the third volume of that work, Abul Fazel briefly describes Hindustan's territorial extent after giving detailed account of the administrative and military structures of the Mughal Empire. Further, Mughal intelligentsia became increasingly interested in Hindu, Jain and Buddhist traditions and the details of Indian folk lore arts and music. one exemplary compilation of this sort was produced by Mirza Muhammed Ibn Fakhruddin entitled *Tuhfat- al Hind*. These investigations embodied political strategy signalling programme of political incorporation by offering patronage to folklore, poetry, dance music and astrology derived from Hindu sources. [7]

Further, Mughals were vitally interested in Information regarding the genealogy of administrative families, information of family pedigrees of visitors from outside India which were deposited at court. It was not the Imperial state alone which tried to sought information and to standardise knowledge in line with political preferences rather it was combined with autonomous networks of social communication with Indian society.[8]

In the late 17th century, Shivaji the founder of Maratha power had set up large guide Jasud department to supply intelligence agents who were attached to forts as their proximity to trade routes gave them access to merchants and travellers from whom information regarding political ambience and about distant regions could be obtained. Similarly forts as watchdog for entire kingdom and treasure house of knowledge was remarked by early 18th century Hindu political text. Forts housed brahmans, astrologers vaidkis scripture readers, and also surgeons well versed in medicines. The 17th century courtier Inayat Khan included details on the economy and statistics of Tibet, a distant frontier region.[9]

Appearance of foreign enemies, notably the British made security the pre-eminent concern for many Indian states. They intensified surveillance in the course of the struggle to retain economic and human resources. The former Maratha service, the Jasud department also survived. However, in later 18th century Peshwa's minister Nana Fadnavis ran a famed Personal intelligence service. Nevertheless, in the domain of information many old sectors survived and improved upon. The networks of intelligence gathering, mapping information by travellers, traders of 17th & 18th century were directly utilized, further regenerated or even expanded during the Colonial rule.[10]

However, there was no stable body of Colonial knowledge till the British had formally taken over as revenue managers of Bengal in 1765. They acquired great wealth of information about the province and the affairs of North India from Mughal office holding families, accumulated empirical political information which

enabled them to deal with the Indian rulers for their trading interests. But the company was poorly informed about the rising regional power outside Mughal orbit. [11]

As a theatre of experimentation, the State-initiated intelligence gathering in the form of documentation, certification that transformed knowledge in to power.

Without good political and military intelligence, the British could never have established their rule or consolidated their position in India. After 1780s creation of new institution by the Colonial Government gradually seen in the relative decline of those indigenous communities of embodied knowledge which had informed pre- colonial kingdoms. Harkaras, astrologers, indigenous physicians were slowly edged away from the political centre. [12]

What served as tools of epistemological conquest by unearthing of much of the past was initiated through generations of European scholarly endeavour that began with William Joans and the Asiatic society of Bengal in 1784. Orientalism before Said, referred to kind of modern European knowledge about Asia and the term connote a highly respectful attitude towards Indian culture and civilianization. [13]

Waren Hastings, first governor general, who was himself a scholar at West Minister believed that Indian knowledge embodied in varied textual tradition of Hindus and Muslims were relevant for developing British administrative institutions. Hastings and his circles promoted the learned Orientalists during 1780s. It was designed to know India, to understand religious and legal traditions of Indian society. They sought to portray as inheritors of political knowledge of the former rulers. The Indian Revenue records were maintained in Persian and Sanskrit thereby Pundits and Ulemas were indispensable for Colonial courts till well in to the 19th century. [14]

One of the first Persian work translated by Francis Gladwin's was Ain- i Akbari by Abul Fazal. The work claimed to depict the original constitution of the Mughal Empire of Akber. It contained governance regulations of judicial executive department, survey of lands, rent roll of Mughal empire. Translation of Alexzander Dow of Persian chronicle *History of Hindustan*, intended exposition of political practices of their predecessor. N.B. Halhed in 1776 published in London a code of gentoo laws which unlocked knowledge of Indian law and religion. In the preface he wrote that a set of most experienced lawyers were selected from Bengal for the purpose of compiling of the work on law.[15]

Shortly before Hasting's departure from India, attention was directed towards Indian learning for the purpose of governance. Fort William College in Calcutta and Haileybury in Britain was established to provide training to ICS recruited for India in Indian languages, literature, history society and culture. Warren Hasting vigorously urged that Arabic and Persian should be the key stone of curricula at the newly established colleges. The recruits at fort William and Haileybury later employed Persian writing masters. Francis Gladwin's Persian munshi provided new skills to the next generation of officials.[16]

Alezander Dow and Robert Orme were particularly significant in the creation of political serviceable Orientalism. William jones, H.T Colebrook Charles Wilkins and host of other lesser scholars with the assistance of group of learned brahmins constructed the state of hindu law, religion and literature. They produced Grammer dictionaries, created discourse and converted Indian forms of knowledge. The great philologist- Sir William Joans while working from London published the Grammer of Persian language in 1771 as knowledge of native language was necessary for the sustenance of the Empire. Halhed's Bengali Grammer suggesting some of the subtle ways in which Orientalist project was part of the Colonial project of rule. In legal practice Joans believed that Manu *Dharma Shashtra* the Indian law book as the most authoritative, original source of legal history in Indian tradition.[17]

However, Joans, Halhed, Colebrook and other British legal scholars shared a suspicion of Indian legal tradition and principles as prejudiced in favour the brahmanas and native elites whose motives were based on harnessing command hence were systematically refigured. Formulation and textualization of Hindu law created a legal discourse that changed the administration of justice in Indian society in fundamental ways. They believed that the European scholarships rendered scientific universal and practical knowledge held by natives in unformed and empirical sense. The generation of Cornwallis and Wellesley deepened formal Oriental knowledge and promoted it as an official discourse in office manuals, Gazettes and newspaper.[18]

Colebrook and Lamberts worked on the state of husbandry and internal commerce of Bengal which was later synthesised as mass of revenue and commercial information. As number of territories increased its jurisdiction, communicating with rulers, merchants, bankers and other natives became difficult due to the linguistic complexity of India. Thus, linguistic survey of India was carried out under George Grierson.[19]

The Company retained the sources of Persian Arabic and Hindustani manuscripts and texts, like the sources preserved in Tipu Sultan's library after the battle of Seringapatam. Indigenous data were being used to support Colonial realpolitik. These sources were catalogued by Stewart, Assistant professor of Persian at the Fort William college. [20]

However, it was also decided to expand the use of English and Hindustani in official business. The emergence of new language communities; Persians, Hindustani Hindi and Urdu forms of prose reflect dynamism of the information order. The first step was evidently to learn the local language, classical Persian, Arabic and Sanskrit as well as spoken vernacular language of the people they were ruling.[21]

British Orientalist made efforts to study Indian languages as important part of Colonial project of control and command. Indian languages texts, Grammers, dictionaries, teaching aids which were to make the acquisition of working knowledge of the languages of India were produced. It was necessary to issue the command, collect taxes and maintain law and order, identify and classify groups within Indian society thereby, constructing India better subsumed to control the vast social world to be mastered. [22]

Gilchrist, who in 1782 came to Bombay after studying medicine in Edinburg, Joined as assistant surgeon of Bengal army. Later left his job and settled in Faizabad where with assistance with natives came out with a dictionary and Grammer of Hindustani language as British language of command.[23] He produced a literature for the classroom on the basis of every day speech that set out to create a common language in place of the immense linguistic diversity of North India. The first set of Hindustani conversation was published in 1798 in the *Oriental Linguist* with specific rules of how to talk with Indians. It accomplished the Language of command which was not only a domestic or personal matter, but a matter of State as key to understanding India and being able to control them.[24]

The dialogues cover the topics of food, dressing, travelling, sports, leisure activities, *memsahib* dealing with servants, commercial transaction, time and whether, military activities, health, medicine, consulting local doctor etc. Gilchrist established an Oriental Seminary in Calcutta in 1799 to teach the newly appointed company servants- the language of communication -Hindustani which became mandatory for the appointment of civil servants for the due discharge of functions in India. Gilchrist was appointed as professor of Hindustani at Fort William to train the officers to relieve their unlimited dependence on native and subordinates.[25]

Warren Hastings initiated the task of preservation of the Classical knowledge by establishing Calcutta Madersa and Banaras Sanskrit College. Semi-official bodies such as Asiatic society of Bengal engaged in the construction for European knowledge. it also caused political and epistemological battle between London and Calcutta over the allocation of resources and financing the said projects.[26]

The Foucauldian analysis of links between power and knowledge is observed most directly in the domains of revenue policy. The consolidation of British rule in India in late 18th and early 19th century opened up new opportunities for the exploitation and appropriation land which became commodity and land revenue as principal source of Government income. As early as 1769 fifteen supervisors appointed by the company's governor to oversee revenue collection. They were instructed to collect information about rent rolls, local history, manners and customs as well as agriculture and craft production to have an understanding of Indian rural society.[27]

For the growth of revenue knowledge Statistic department - was established. Evidences on revenue rates from each pargana were accumulated by the instruction of Jonathan Duncan. References from Revenue papers of Raja Cheyt Singh was taken to attest earlier practices of management. Warren Hastings coopted entrepreneurs like opium agent Ramchandra Pundit who became company's opium contractor; supplied information on the cultivation of historical account of that crop, of Dutch opium trade in the region in the early 18th century.

His sociology of castes also fed in to later Colonial descriptions that the Koeries who cultivated the crop were lowest of the four general casts of the Hindus.[28] They were thus known as Koeries because they grew Koyrar - Opium tobacco and vegetables.

Further, When British took over Awadh from Nawab in 1802, they had to depend on local writers and revenue contractors as experts in the region. However, that knowledge was defective or partial as reflected in the discontent in the rural areas since 1830s which eventually culminated in an attempt to bring down company's regime in 1857.[29]

Every step in the expansion of British political and economic control was based on accumulation of knowledge through Indologists' endeavour and empirical observation. Further, Surveys, Statistics and records made their appearance in British India after the Trigonometrical Survey of India (1799) and Statistical section of British Association (1833) was established as arm of the state. The word Statistics formed from Statist which used to refer both Statistician, Politician Statesmen and any one skilled in the affairs of the State.[30]

Between 1807 and 1814 a Statistical Survey of Bengal was carried out at the behest of the company by Dr Buchanan- a Scottish physician. He had previously conducted a survey of company's territories in Mysore in which topography, history and antiquities, religious customs, production of mines, agriculture, landed property, domestic animals, fine arts, commerce were prepared in three volumes of each district, preceded the emergence of Statistics as a modern science. [31]

In 1844 an official history dealing with each district in a separate volume witnessed penetration of administration into Indian society and accumulation of knowledge at the subordinate levels. The district and Settlement reports paved the way for official series of Gazetteers in late 19th and early 20th century .

After 1857, British raj became more security conscious, thereby increasingly employed Statistical and Ethnographic information to attempt to better control the large swathes of people and territory of India. This strategy of organised information was most apparent in the official Gazetteer that emerged in the second half of the 18th century. Series of district Gazetteers, Survey and Settlement reports and tribes and caste volumes documented for various British Indian provinces. As by product of revenue surveys and settlement proceedings many Archaeological sites were identified and mapped. [32]

The first surveyor of India Colin Mackenzie, spent most of his time in India compiling a massive collection of documents, manuscripts and other artefacts.

He managed the first surveys of Deccan in the late 18th and early 19th century after cessation of land from the Nizam of Hyderabad and then after triumph at Seringapatam from Tipu Sultan. He identified the Amravati ruins as containing important documentation of much earlier Buddhist history in Southern India. The first large scale excavation of archaeological sites was directed by Colin Mackenzie who carried on 20 years project in South India.[33]

While mapping of the newly possessed land through topographical surveys, Mackenzie was assisted by trained group of brahmans. His chief interpreter brahmin named Boria commanded four Indian languages along with English. Boria recruited and trained an organization of learned brahmans to work for Mackenzie.

Nicholas Dirks essay on career and writings of administrator Colin Mackenzie demonstrated the extent to which the native assistant was instrumental in constructing Colonial knowledge. However, the voices of natives were marginalised in a hegemonic Colonial discourse. [34]

To facilitate a genuine understanding of Ethnology and religion of India, James Fergusson who had come to India as indigo planter travelled widely in 1837-1942 and wrote series of accounts of arts and architecture which established hegemonic history. Although the British in India were always aware that their power was dependent on their knowledge; hence made maniac efforts to excavate and collect relics and rocks of variable significance.[35]

While accepting that Oriental knowledge to some extent a means of dominating and mastering India, an army engineer Alexander Cunningham developed interest in Indian archaeology, successfully petitioned Lord Canning in 1859 to establish Archaeological Survey of India in which he became its first director. The Survey became responsible for preservation of historical sites. The first large scale museum in India was built in Calcutta in 1840s under the aegis of Asiatic society of Bengal. [36]

In the second half of the 19th century, the Government of India began to focus on the production of detailed district level volumes termed as district gazetteer- as a comprehensive description of district of British India. It included historical archaeological, political, economic sociological and commercial statistical data. In 1869, Viceroy Mayo commissioned W.W Hunter to visit various provincial governments. These imperatives transformed into histories Gazetteers, legal codes and Encyclopaedias. Further, for management of population in its depth and details the govt. of Bengal undertook an Ethnographic survey of all important castes and tribes of Bengal. H. H. Risley of Bengal civil service was its author[37].

Around late 19th and early 20th century Science became more important for Imperial governance. Mathew Edney's study of Colonial Geography shows that Colonial Cartographic techniques and surveys for mapping physical space required for effective control and exploitation of a vast subcontinent. Robert Clive assigned James Rennell, a naval officer turned surveyor the task of surveying newly acquired Bengal territories. Beginning with Rennell's maps of Bengal and then of India (1770s and 1780s) and Route survey covered by foot and combined with compass readings gave way to more abstract Scientific Trigonometrical Survey to produce a dominating controlling view of spaces from above. [38] These sources were also used for generating detailed data required for military campaigns. Mapping and establishments of routes were part of mercantile history of India.

Thus, systematic surveys by Rennell, William Lambton, Colin Makenzie, Alexander Cunningham and Francis Buchanan Hamilton for vast knowledge was transformed into textual forms as extensive archives that were deployed by the Colonial State in fixing, bounding and settling India.[39]

Every step in the expansion of British political and economic control, culminated in decennial Census from 1871 onwards. However, stimulated by the Sadian turn, the framework which expanded the meaning of Orientalism helped to bring out linkages and imbrications with power relations within colonial documentation with elements of implicit ethnocentrism and racism. This exposure has made historians much more aware of dimensions of power related assumptions. A systematic questioning started of achieves previously considered more or less objective, lying concealed within Statistical and Scientific Colonial administrative knowledge apparatus. Oriental scholarship contributed decisively to the formation of highly influential stereotypes and modes of classification for sake of ruling. [40]

By late 19th century the formation of official ethnography involves new categories of the array of castes and customs that became part of the information. The specificities of Colonial Census have been highlighted by Arjun Appadurai.[41] He argued that each Census in Colonial period from 1891 and 1911 provide clear evidence of potential power. The key for official choice of classificatory categories, for the colony lays in group difference along lines of religion and caste which was to stimulate competition, rivalry and conflict –while their access to education, jobs and in sphere of political influence.

With the advance of anti-colonial Nationalist Movements, the Colonial need grew to play off varied community identities of religion, castes, ethnicity, language and region against each other- potential for divide and rule.

However, significant difference was observed between Census procedure in Britain which concentrated on territorial location and occupation despite religious differences and conflicts.

Fashioning of the categories of difference and registering the native voice the British misrepresented the description of native people as backward to justify their domination. However, British always tried to show that their pursuit of empirical knowledge has political implications. H.H. Risley worked on Caste and Tribes of Bengal and after directing the 1901 census, he soon became Home member in Curzon's administration. He played a very notable part in this official capacity in the partitioning of Bengal in 1905.[42]

The Census reports not only summarised the Statistical information about the caste system, religion, domestic organization, but also created social categories by which India was ordered for administrative purposes. The project objectified social, cultural, linguistic differences among the people of India-representing the model of Victorian encyclopaedic quest for total knowledge. Orientalism of earlier times does not entirely fit with the subsequent blatant more aggressive side of it during the high noon of imperialism when shift appeared in discourse for dominance.[43]

A rapid rise was also witnessed in the use of technological and statistical practice as means to address problems associated with public health, revenue generation and agriculture. Numerous other new methods for a much more individualized surveillance were also worked upon. The registration of births and deaths, the photographing of indentured labour started in 1875, and method of finger printing was invented by police for crime detection in 1898 for solving the murder case of a tea planter in Jalpaiguri.[44]

Further, geographical explorations and espionage on Frontiers was initiated through diplomatic missions, secrete individual explorers and through native agents and spies due to convulsions in the Durrani Empire of Afghanistan and fear of French and Russian diplomatic activity in the region which continued to cause uneasiness in Calcutta. 18th century travellers and 19th century geographers were actually intelligence gatherers. In late 1790s fear of French ambition drew British military officers to harp on knowledge of George Thomas- the Irish adventurer who had served the Marathas. About the same time Francis Wilford, the Orientalist of Banaras commissioned Mughal beg to make a fabulous work on classical geographers. Wilford compendium turned out a complex and dense document. [45]

What power needed was not science but a mass of information which was directly exploited by colonial strategists' traders and industrialists. Technically qualified Indians were recruited and trained by the great Trigonometrical Survey of India to survey beyond the frontiers. These native explorer in the files of the Government of India were given the designation as spies or secret agents.[46]

From the early 18th century onwards British and Tsarist Russia emerged as main contestants in Asia. Central Asia became the object of Colonial rivalry by the middle of 19th century and after annexation of Punjab brought British empire in India into direct contact with Afghanistan and Central Asia. Russia too consolidating its position in Kazak steppes was moving ahead in Central Asia and that Anglo Russian rivalry opened up the way to Ladakh and Chinese Turkestan. [47]

The uncertainties on the border and fear of security in this region were behind the Information gathering which culminated in Manstuart Elphinstone 's account of kingdom of Kabul 1815, John Malcom's history of Persia. Elphinstone gathered his information during a diplomatic mission to Afghan court. Malcom succeeded Elphinstone as governor of Bombay had undertaken ambitious diplomatic mission to Persia in 1801. These works in turn formed a major portion of Hamilton's sources for *the East India Gazetteer*. Investigations by Elphinstone, Malcom and Metcalf were designed to garner political economic information about Western Himalayas [48]

The first Colonial official to write extensively on Ladakh was William Moorcroft, a veterinary surgeon of the company. He along with his travelling companion George Trabeck prepared voluminous journal which was later edited and published by H.H. Wilson. Moreover, his voluminous reports on manufacture and trade of Kashmiri shawls, commercial reporting passed to companies archive in 18th century. Pathans horse traders and magnates who controlled grazing grounds furnished Moorcroft with a stock of information which led through Delhi and Lahore into Chinese Turkistan and Persian borderlands. Natives like Abdul Kader Khan and Banaras Maulvi, Izatullah Khan accompanied him on his journey in Turkestan in 1813 and 1820 respectively. Further, Moorcroft depended for information on khatri commercial houses which linked Delhi, Lahore, Peshawar and Kabul with Persia and Central Asia. He also tapped wealthy Kashmiri Muslims commercial connections to gather inputs which stretched to far distant western China and Inland Burma. [49]

Further, British diplomats and explorers included Alexander Burnes, Claude Wade and Charles Masson for diplomatic interests and desire for execution of trade. They traversed the dangerous routes over the next three decades. European travellers with scientific attainments accompanied by Persian speaking clerks and soldiers who knew about artillery enlisted to bring information and initiate diplomatic contacts.[50]

After Russian movements against the Central Asian Khanates, the situation in the North West was deteriorated sufficiently for the British to consider direct intervention. The forward policy laid the foundations for the British campaign in Afghanistan of 1839-42. The complex mixture of economic political and exotic aims made British to explore these regions. Mohan Lal Kashmiri, a Kashmiri brahmin who accompanied Alexander Burnes as Persian munshi, pioneered exploration of North West frontier and his noteworthy contributions paved the way

for host of Indian spies and explorers. His travelogues on fact-finding mission of 1832 contributed in geographical exploration and espionage. [51]

Elphinstone accumulated information on Afghanistan and his mission-built road maps on lands. He interviewed religious leaders, quizzed traders who moved between Peshawar and Kabul and also gathered information on population from itinerant Muslim physician and purveyors who moved regularly between Peshawar, Kabul, Bokhara and up in to Turkestan. Elphinstone was fascinated with stories of Kafiristan. The mission also gathered information on pathans soldiers in British service. These men were settled in Rohilkhand and retained connections with their home land. The 1st Pushto dictionary in British hands had been assembled by a Pathans Nobel men of Braille in 1803.[52]

Conclusion

This was how an immense Colonial archive on 19th and early 20th century India had been accumulated through a multitude of administrative files and reports, surveys and census operations, scientific observations geographical explorations, espionage and research which provided source material on a scale which was impossible in earlier times. The shades of classical orientalism of Sir William Jones generation and statistical empiricists and empire builders' generation poised for gathering information.[53]

Colonial formation of authoritative knowledge and its legacy have affected many aspects of Indian life. The sociology of colonial knowledge included establishing a finite body of language called Hindustani for colonial consumption but turned out into language as matter of national unity.

Formulation and textualization of Hindu and Muslim law created legal discourse that changed the administration of justice in Indian society in fundamental ways. [54]Early Orientalist looked for the finer specimen of Indian tradition. Hasting translation of Bhagwat Gita was sought to show British public opinion the advanced state of Indian civilization. This move later laid the foundation whereby, Gita became the Hindu text par excellence for India's great Nationalist leaders. Discourse on literature as expression of cultural identity of Indian society was recaptured in 20th century in terms cultural nationalism.[55]

Further, Orientalist view coincided with Brahmanical notion in the formation of Colonial discourses. its distinction between Aryans and non-Aryan applied by Germans in to their own society in their attempt to define the Jews as non-Aryans. The notion of entitlement and classification were given prominence in the Census that became basis of communal and caste politics of 20th century. [56]

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